

research article

Investigating the Effective Components of Designing Residential Complexes' Spaces Based on Promoting the General Health of Residents (Case Study: Golestan and Zanbaq Residential Complexes in Shiraz)

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Abstract

In the present age in urban and industrial societies, the environment's negative effects on the psyche of individuals and the prevalence of mental disorders make a need to pay attention to public health.

Based on this fact, healing spaces are required for a daily stressful life. Residential areas have the largest share among where human beings deal during the day and have the most significant impact on the individual. So, these spaces should be designed to provide mental and physical health for residents. This study aims to provide effective components for promoting the general health of residents in residential complexes. This research has been done by a combined method (quantitative-qualitative). In the first stage, after introducing the basic concepts, healing architecture characteristics have been extracted from the research background, which will be the basis for the researcher-made questionnaire. Data collection was conducted by presenting a researcher-made questionnaire, a standard general health questionnaire (GHQ), and Keyes's Social Well-being questionnaire (KSWBQ) to the residents of Zanbaq and Golestan residential complexes in Shiraz. Finally, the data obtained by Spss-23 software were analyzed using factor analysis, Pearson correlation, and the Friedman test. According to the results, the effective design components of residential complexes include various spaces and activities, environmental safety and security, privacy, environmental well-being, environmental pleasure and attractiveness, and social interactions based on promoting the general health of residents. Among these factors, the highest mean rank belongs to the component of social interactions, and the lowest one belongs to the component of various spaces and activities.

Keywords: Healing Architecture, Residential Complexes, Public Health.

1- Introduction

Housing is one of the most significant physical, psychological, emotional, and spiritual elements in human life, providing a crucial space for personal belonging. This space reflects the residents' sense of aesthetics, nature, culture, and identity (Marshall, 2008). Alongside food and clothing, housing is a fundamental biological necessity essential for the preservation and survival of both individuals and society (Maleki, 2011).

According to the World Health Organization, health is a state of complete physical, mental, and social well-being, not merely the absence of disease or illness. Healing involves alleviating physical symptoms, illness, and emotional trauma, which reduces stress and increases comfort (Marcus & Barnes, 1995, as quoted in Nili, Nili & Soltanzadeh, 2011). In designing healing spaces, the main objective is to alleviate the psychological pressures of daily life, focusing on reducing tension and enhancing the ability of spaces to provide relaxation, recovery, and the restoration of mental and emotional health (Nikbakht, 2004).

Nowadays, harmful environments are increasingly contributing to the occurrence of various diseases, including heart diseases, cancer, brain diseases, vascular diseases, chronic respiratory diseases, and injuries resulting from improper environmental design (Lavin, Higgins, Metcalfe & Jordan, 2006). Some buildings cause physical and mental problems for their occupants, known as "building syndrome." In urban and industrial societies, the adverse effects of the environment on the human psyche and the prevalence of mental disorders such as anxiety and depression underscore the need to consider the surrounding environment in maintaining mental health (ImamQoli, 2013). Among the spaces people interact with daily, residential spaces have the largest share and the greatest impact on individuals, so it is crucial to design them to ensure the health of the residents.

Therefore, addressing public health in architectural spaces, particularly residential ones, is very important and necessary due to their wide-ranging impact on people. Healing spaces are essential in today's stressful life, and in a medical society that emphasizes prevention over treatment, such structures are highly beneficial. Considering the importance and necessity of this issue, the present research aims to provide effective components for designing residential complexes based on improving the general health of the residents. It is hoped that by identifying and using these components in the design of residential complexes, we can take a step toward enhancing the health and well-being of society.

Based on the stated problem, the question raised in the present research is as follows:

What components in the design of residential complexes can have an effect on improving the general health of residents?

2- Reviewing theoretical foundations and research background

2-1- Background of the research

The subject of healing architecture is one of the most important topics that has always received attention, and various research studies have been conducted in the field of healing and the role of the environment in it. The ancients' attention to the issue of a healthy environment can be seen in ancient writings. If we go back to the fifth century BC, we come across Hippocrates, who described the marsh as an unhealthy and unsafe environment and the mountainside as a place with good weather that was sunny and safe (ImamQoli, 2013). In recent decades, researchers have studied the effect of the environment on health and healing in various spaces such as healing gardens, hospitals, nursing homes, and neighborhood spaces, some of which are presented in Table 1:

Table 1: The background of the research with the presentation of the results

Wilson (1972) Intensive care delirium, the effect of outside deprivation in a windowless unit
The results of this research have shown that the presence of a window facing outside in the hospital room of patients in the special care department is effective in improving their condition.
Hartig (1991) Testing restorative environments theory.

In this research, the recovery of non-diseased people who were stressed was investigated, and the findings showed that if people look at a natural environment with vegetation instead of a built environment without nature, the recovery is significantly increased.

Ulrich, et al., (1991) Stress recovery during exposure to natural and urban environments

In this research, the study on non-patient groups (such as students) as well as patients showed that simply looking at the natural landscape, such as plants, flowers or water, compared to the built environment without nature (rooms, buildings, or cities), is significantly effective in improving or relieving stress.

Marcus & Barnes (1995) Gardens in Healthcare Facilities: Uses Therapeutic Benefits, and Design Recommendations

The findings of this research indicate that relief from stress, including mood improvement, is one of the most important benefits that almost all garden-hospital users, including patients, families and employees, get.

Van den Berg, Koole & Van der Wulp (2003) Environmental preference and restoration: (How) are they related?

The research results indicate that being in the park or forest reduces stress, anger, depression and tension and increases concentration and happiness in people.

Verhaeghe, Coenen & Van de Putte (2016) Is living in a high-rise building bad for your self-rated health?

This research investigated the effect of building height on people's health, and it was concluded that the health level of the residents of tall buildings is significantly lower than that of the residents of short buildings.

Azemati & Zarghami (2011) The relationship between residents' health and neighborhood quality

In this research, by examining case examples, it was concluded that the type of architecture of the area, the connection between residential spaces and open space, green space and social interactions can affect the health of residents and the healing of the environment.

Zojaji, Nikbakht & Kafi (2015) Design principles for therapeutic areas with an emphasis on the components of the healing garden.

In this research, the design principles of treatment areas with special emphasis on relaxation through stimulating the five senses of users, simplicity, visual pleasure, increasing social interaction and rehabilitation of patients were formulated.

Taheri & Taheri (2018): Evaluation of environmental factors affecting mental health in residential complexes

The results of the research show that among the environmental factors affecting mental health, the physical environment has the most negative effect on the health of residents. Therefore, by improving the physical quality of the residential environment, it is necessary to raise the level of people's satisfaction with their place of residence in order to improve the quality of the social relations of the residents.

Abdulzadeh Fard & Shamsaldini (2019) The role of the environmental quality of the neighborhood in the mental health of the residents.

The results of the research showed that social cohesion and trust in the neighborhood can have a greater effect on improving mental and emotional health, and suggestions have been made to improve the state of physical, social and cultural quality, meaningfulness and readability, flexibility and eventability, sociability, vitality and diversity...

In the mentioned research studies, healing and mental health were studied and investigated in different spaces, such as gardens, therapeutic spaces, residences, neighborhood spaces of housing, and residential complexes. However, the current research aims to study the issue of health in housing, especially residential complexes, considering the importance of housing and its many effects on people. It will examine the factors affecting the design of residential complex spaces based on improving health on three levels: physical, psychological, and social.

According to the research background and the study of Persian and English sources, indicators affecting health in the environment have been extracted and presented in Table 2:

Table 2: Indicators affecting health in the environment, extracted from previous research studies

factor	Effective indicators on health	Name of researcher/researchers
social	Social support	Grahn & Stigsdotter 2010, Marcus & Barnes 1995
	Collective spaces	Marcus & Barnes 1999
	Social interactions	Brown, Worden, Frohne & Sullivan 2011, Rappaport 2005, Azemati & Zarghami 2012
	Social Security	Carp, Zawadski & Shokrkon 1976
Activity	Possibility of physical mobility	Marcus & Barnes 1999
	Happy and meaningful activities	Bengtsson & Grahn 2014
	Participation in the environment	Caniano 2006

Cognitive and psychological	User control and mastery of the environment	Malkin 2003, Ulrich 1999, Marcus & Barnes 1999, Nikbakht 2004
	Considering the user in the design	Weberdmeister 2009, Rappaport 2005, Eroglu & Harrell 1986
	Satisfaction with the architectural space	Bentley, Alcock, Morin, McGlynn & Smith 2010
	Familiarity of the user with the environment	Marcus & Barnes 1999
	Attention to history and culture	Bengtsson & Grahn 2014,
	Appropriate density of people	Rapaport 2005, Topf 1984, Nesmith 1995, Beatrice, Thamos & Biles, 1998, Williams 1988, Baker 1984
	Comprehensibility of the environment	Nakamura & Fujii 1992
	Minimize ambiguity readability	Kaplan 1989, Bengtsson & Grahn 2014, Caniano 2006, Marcus 2007
	Privacy protection	Caniano 2006
	Mystery and complexity	Malkin 2003, Wilson 2006, Marcus & Barnes 1999
	Continuity and spatial coherence	Kaplan 1989 Marcus 2007, Bengtsson & Grahn 2014, Caniano 2006,
	Spatial diversity	Kaplan 1989
	Flexibility and balance	Bengtsson & Grahn 2014, Marcus 2007
Environmental and physical	Adequate amount of natural light	Caniano 2006
	Physical comfort	Scanlon 2007, Beauchemin & Hays 1996, Phiri 2003, Van den Berg 2005, Oberlin 2008, Topf 1984, Nesmith 1995, Beatrice & <i>et al.</i> , 1998, Williams 1988, Baker 1984
	Cleaning and cleanliness	Van den Berg 2005, Akalin-Baskaya & Yildirim 2007, Topf 1984, Beatrice, <i>et al.</i> , 1998, Nesmith 1995 Williams 1988, Baker 1984
	Safety in the environment	Ulrich, Zimring, Zhu, DuBose, Seo, Choi & <i>et al.</i> , 2008
	Taking advantage of nature	Scanlon 2007, Fairhall, Bache, Dodd & Young 2009, Campbell 1996, Kawakami, Winkleby, Skog, Szulkin & Sundquist 2011, Miller, Tsemberis, Malia & Grega 1980
	Variety of materials and textures	Frumkin 2001, Marcus & Barnes 1999, Caniano 2006, Bengtsson & Grahn 2014, Van den Berg 2005, Sherman, Varni, Ulrich & Malcarne 2005, Gesler 2003, Wilson 2006, Ulrich 1999, Baum, Singer & Valins 1978
	Use of art and works of art	Gruter 1996
	Use of color	Kellett, Macnaughton & Coleman 2004, Eisen 2007, Scanlon 2007
	Quality and arrangement of furniture	Hill & Think 2008, Kellett, Macnaughton & Coleman 2004, Oberlin 2008, Eisen 2007, Scanlon 2007
	easy accessibility	Bonaiuto, Bonnes & Fornara 2002, Malkin 2003, Scanlon 2007
	Kaplan 1989, Marcus 2007, Bengtsson & Grahn 2014, Caniano 2006	

2-2- The concept of healing

In Dehkhoda's dictionary, healing means health and recovery from illness. The word "heal" comes from the Anglo-Saxon word "healen," which means whole. Literally, totality means holistic, and here it refers to the sum of body and mind. Therefore, healing is a quality that encompasses the whole human being, both body and mind (Azemati & Zarghami, 2011). According to Ibn Sina, health is a state in which the human body is of such quality in terms of temperament and composition that all its actions are correct. He considers health to be a state in which the actions of the body are directed correctly, and the opposite of that is moving away from health (Ibn Sina, 1992).

There are three important components to health: physical, mental, and social health. Therefore, the definition of general health is the feeling of satisfaction with mental, physical, and social health (ImamQoli, 2013). Goldsmith introduces social health as one of the most basic health indicators of any country and defines it as the evaluation of significant positive and negative behaviors of a person in relation to others (Larson, 1993).

2-3- Healing housing

Today, we know that many factors contribute to human health and well-being, and the physical and man-made environment, including architecture and urban planning, play a significant role alongside other factors (ImamQoli, 2013). In this context, rather than emphasizing the treatment of a person, the focus should be on the reduction of tension and the ability of the space to provide relief, relaxation, recovery of strength, and restoration of mental and emotional health (Nikbakht, 2004). The best kind of healing architecture design can be implemented in private spaces. This is because the main difference between healing environments and others is that the user has a direct role in them; the user determines what gives them energy, what brings them peace, and what they expect from the environment. In this case, the influence will be at the highest level (Frumkin, 2001; Ulrich, 1984).

When discussing healing and promoting public health in residential spaces, the main goal is to create a shelter that reduces the psychological pressures of everyday life, alleviates tension, provides relaxation, restores strength, and revitalizes the mental and emotional health of individuals. Since the impact of housing on the general health of people is much greater than that of other spaces due to the continuous and long-term relationship people have with it, special attention should be paid to its design.

3- Methodology

The current research was written with the aim of achieving effective components in the design of residential complexes based on the general health of the residents and was carried out using a combined method (quantitative and qualitative). In order to achieve the stated goal, the research was carried out in six steps. In the first step, the basic concepts of the research have been introduced through library studies, and the healing indicators in the environment have been extracted from various Persian and English research studies, and these indicators are the basis for writing the questionnaire. In the next step, case samples were selected, and user surveys were conducted using a researcher-made questionnaire and a standard questionnaire. In the fourth step, the data were analyzed by software using factor analysis, Friedman's test, and a correlation test. In the fifth step, the components are introduced and ranked, and the correlation of the components with different dimensions of health has been investigated. Finally, in the sixth step, the factors affecting the improvement of the general health of the residents of residential complexes have been investigated, according to the research findings and observations made by the researchers and referring to previous research. The steps for collecting research information are: a) library and internet study. b) Direct observation and taking photos and notes. c) Questionnaire: In the questionnaire, two categories of questions are raised, the first of which is a researcher-made questionnaire that includes questions that are consistent with the research assumptions and evaluates them. Each question consists of five items and includes the individual's opinions regarding the architectural qualities of the environment, which have been obtained by the researchers, and according to the healing indicators that have been obtained from the review of previous research studies in Farsi and English. The second part of the question also evaluates different dimensions of health. To measure physical and mental health, the Goldberg General Health Questionnaire (GHQ) was used, which was presented by Goldberg and Hiller in 1979 and has 28 questions and 4 subscales, each subscale having seven questions. The mentioned subscales are: physical symptoms, anxiety symptoms, sleep disorders, social functioning, and depression symptoms (Goldberg, Gater, Sartorius, Ustun, Piccinelli, Gureje, & Rutter, 1997). To measure social health, the Social Health Questionnaire (KSWBQ) was used, which was made by Keyes at the MacArthur Science Foundation of the United States of America in 2004 (Sabouri, 2010).

The sample selection in this research has been done by random method, and according to the statistical population studied in this research, which includes the residents of residential apartment complexes, Golestan and Zanbaq residential complexes in Shiraz city are considered as case

examples. Golestan residential complex was built in 1997 by Fars Development Company and is located in Golestan town, in the northwest of Shiraz city. This complex, with a total area of 75,000 square meters, has 686 residential units in 15 short blocks and is considered one of the large-scale complexes. The type of spatial organization of this complex is central, and the percentage of open space is 76% (Taghipour, 2019). The Zanbaq residential complex was also built in 1996 by the South Housing Investment Company. This complex, with a total infrastructure area of 22,400 square meters, has 8 short blocks and 182 residential units and is considered a medium-scale complex. This residential complex has a mixed spatial organization, and its open space is 82% (Ibid.). In order to calculate the sample size, although there is no general agreement about the sample size required for factor analysis (Schreiber, Nora, Stage, Barlow, & King, 2006), many researchers suggest the minimum required sample size is 200 (Hoelter, 1983; Sivo, Fan, & Willse, 2006; Hoe, 2008). Considering that some questionnaires may not be answered or returned, the sample size in this study is 220 people, with a 10% increase. The age range of the studied people is between 25 and 65 years old, and the condition for entering the research is at least 5 years of living in the investigated complexes. The information from the questionnaires completed by the residents was finally entered into SPSS-23 software and analyzed using factor analysis, the Friedman test, and Pearson correlation test. Finally, the obtained components have been made using observations and have been investigated and analyzed with reference to previous research. Figure 1 shows the diagram of the research process:

Figure 1: Research process diagram (authors)

4- Findings

In this research, to present the factors influencing the improvement of the general health of residents in residential complexes, in the first stage, a questionnaire was designed by the researchers based on indicators extracted from previous research studies. Subsequently, the content and validity of the

questions, as well as their relevance to the research objectives, were confirmed by experts, and some questions were removed. The reliability of the questionnaire was assessed through a pilot study involving residents, and the data were transferred to SPSS-23 software, where Cronbach's alpha showed a value of 0.88 (Table 3), confirming the reliability of the researcher-made questionnaire.

Table 3: Reliability analysis by calculating Cronbach's alpha
Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.880	22

Furthermore, researcher-made and standard questionnaires were distributed among 220 residents of Zanbaq and Golestan residential complexes. The data were then entered into SPSS-23 software, and factor analysis was conducted for data analysis. As shown in Table 4, the adequacy of the sample size was confirmed by the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test, yielding a result of 0.766, indicating sufficient sample size. The significance level (Sig) of Bartlett's test was also zero, indicating that correlation values could be calculated.

Table 4: K-M-O and Bartlett's sphericity test for sample size adequacy

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.766
Bartlett's test of sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	670.499
	df	231
	Sig.	.000

The variance of the data after rotation indicates that 7 factors have been identified according to the opinions of the residents. Based on the variance table of the rotated data (Table 5), it can be concluded that these factors explain a total of 66% of the variance related to the components affecting the improvement of the general health of residents in residential complexes.

Table 5: Data variance from factor analysis rotation

Component	Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.560	16.184	16.184
2	2.322	10.554	26.737
3	2.108	9.584	36.321
4	1.832	8.326	44.647
5	1.787	8.124	52.771
6	1.492	6.781	59.553
7	1.452	6.598	66.151

In order to identify the effective components in the design of residential complexes aimed at improving the general health of residents, the exploratory factor analysis method was employed. The data were rotated in the factor matrix to determine factors based on respondents' responses. This approach allows components to be expressed on a broader scale, and dependent variables can be identified. Table 6 presents the contribution of each variable to the factors after rotation, where each variable is assigned to a factor with which it exhibits a highly significant correlation.

Table 6: Rotated factor analysis matrix

Question No.	Component						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
9	.827	.011	-.003	.192	.059	.201	.136
5	.711	.011	.005	.048	.144	.425	.158
4	.670	.121	.192	.227	.001	.082	.188
10	.633	.207	.135	.170	.233	.067	.058
21	.475	.437	.301	.021	-.043	-.161	-.071

19	.470	.352	.047	-.264	-.031	-.092	-.329
20	.152	.812	-.012	-.005	.141	-.046	.032
18	.160	.803	.393	.065	-.252	.220	.140
1	-.008	.663	.023	.170	.232	.103	.056
15	-.003	.592	.096	.176	.001	-.046	.156
22	.130	.065	.663	.337	.279	.216	-.174
6	.351	.094	.537	.026	.338	.213	.118
17	.503	.022	.528	-.031	.086	-.285	.271
3	.133	.132	.170	.766	.034	.080	.088
8	.421	-.098	.134	.611	.087	-.079	.185
2	.090	.390	.170	.531	.285	-.025	-.152
12	.022	.208	.144	.079	.809	.092	.093
11	.507	.005	.072	.084	.605	-.296	-.030
13	.210	.027	.090	.236	.500	.193	.498
7	.250	.223	.076	.151	.064	.709	.205
14	-.074	.453	-.044	.357	.023	.582	.268
16	.249	.121	.147	.035	.059	.034	.808

Thus, the questions were grouped into six factors, and each factor was named by the researchers based on the content of the relevant questions, as shown in Table 7. These factors include: diverse spaces and activities; environmental comfort; social interactions; privacy; safety and security of the environment; pleasantness and attractiveness of the environment.

Table 7: Classification of questionnaire questions according to factor analysis

Factor analysis classification	Design component	Content of questionnaire questions
component 1 questions 4-5-9-10-19-21	Various spaces and activities	Sports spaces Recreational spaces Various activities Happy and meaningful activities Nature and greenery
component 2 questions 1-15-18-20	Environmental comfort	air quality Environmental cleanliness Proper lighting Appropriate density of people
component 3 questions 6-22-17	Social interactions in the environment	Interaction of different age groups The possibility of watching children Collective spaces
component 4 questions 2-3-8	privacy	Peace of mind Desirable privacy Respect for privacy
component 5 questions 11-12-13	Safety and security of the environment	Use of walls and fences Ease of movement Social Security
component 6 Questions 7-14	Pleasantness and attractiveness of the environment	Use of design and color The desirability of the landscape

Next, Friedman's test was employed to rank the factors influencing the design of residential complexes based on improving the general health of residents. Table 8 displays the statistical significance, indicating that the chi-square value obtained is 70.184, significant at a level of less than 0.5. This indicates that the ranking of the investigated components is significant, and there are differences in the importance and ranking of these components.

Table 8: Statistics of Friedman's test

Test Statistics	
Chi-Square	70.184

df	5
Asymp. Sig.	.000

Table 9 displays the numerical averages of the components and the standard deviation of the variables. It is observed that the highest average value is assigned to the component of social interactions, and the lowest value is assigned to the component of diverse spaces and activities.

Table 9: Description of the statistics of the components affecting the design of residential complexes based on improving the general health of the residents

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Various spaces and activities	1.00	4.50	2.4290	.91022
Environmental comfort	1.75	4.75	2.9691	.70199
Social interactions in the environment	1.33	5.00	3.2387	.72310
privacy	1.25	4.50	2.8673	.75941
Safety and security of the environment	1.33	4.33	2.9959	.73879
Pleasantness and attractiveness of the environment	1.50	5.00	3.1728	.72094

In Table 10, the ranking of the components affecting the design of residential complexes based on improving the general health of residents is presented. The average ratings indicate that the highest average rating is assigned to the components "social interactions" and "pleasantness and attractiveness of the environment," while the lowest rating is assigned to the component "diverse spaces and activities."

Table 10: The average rating of the components affecting the design of residential complexes based on improving the general health of residents

Component	Mean Rank
Social interactions in the environment	4.29
Pleasantness and attractiveness of the environment	4.15
privacy	3.60
Environmental comfort	3.59
Safety and security of the environment	3.19
Various spaces and activities	2.19

The results of the component rankings presented in the table above are depicted in the form of a bar chart in Figure 2:

Figure 2: Mean rank bar chart

In the following, Pearson's correlation test was used to investigate the relationship between the components influencing the design of residential complexes based on improving the general health of residents and health dimensions. The results are shown in Table 11:

Table 11: Correlation between the six components and health dimensions according to the Pearson correlation coefficient

		physical health	mental health	Social health
Social interactions	Pearson Correlation	-.055	.014	.055*

	Sig. (2-tailed)	.586	.893	.045
Pleasantness and attractiveness of the environment	Pearson Correlation	.114*	.114*	.037
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.024	.023	.709
Privacy	Pearson Correlation	.052	.003*	.079*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.601	.035	.03
Environmental comfort	Pearson Correlation	.302**	.252**	.148
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	.010	.134
Environmental safety and security	Pearson Correlation	.210*	.012*	.067
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.041	.009	.517
Various spaces and activities	Pearson Correlation	.114*	.039*	-.046
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.03	.03	.648

According to the table above, the components correlated with physical health are: diverse spaces and activities, environmental comfort, pleasantness and attractiveness of the environment, and safety and security of the environment. Factors affecting mental health include diverse spaces and activities, pleasantness and attractiveness of the environment, safety and security of the environment, environmental comfort, and privacy. Factors influencing social health are privacy and social interactions. Therefore, paying attention to these components in the design of residential complexes can form the basis for improving residents' health in three dimensions: mental, physical, and social. Based on the relationships between different dimensions of health and the environmental components of residential complexes, the following model (Figure 3) can be proposed for the components influencing the design of residential complexes based on improving the general health of residents:

Figure 3: The presented model for the components affecting the design of residential complexes based on improving the general health of residents

5- Discussion

In this section, first, the hypothesis raised at the beginning of the research will be examined, which states that in the design of residential complexes, components facilitating social interaction and ensuring security can impact the improvement of residents' general health. To validate this

hypothesis, according to Table 8, it can be asserted that factors such as social interactions, safety and security, as well as solitude and privacy, influence the enhancement of residents' general health in residential complexes. Therefore, the hypothesis formulated at the beginning of the research is confirmed. Subsequently, considering the research objectives and the correlation of identified components with public health, and based on observations within residential complexes, the factors influencing the improvement of residents' general health were investigated. These factors will be presented in terms of their impact on different dimensions of health, drawing on previous research studies:

Pleasantness and Attractiveness of the Environment and its Effect on Physical and Mental Health: In residential complexes, the use of diverse designs, colors, textures, and motifs, along with incorporating natural elements and creating favorable landscapes, can significantly impact residents' health. Residents often personalize their spaces by painting terraces with desired designs and colors or adjusting terrace lighting to enhance visual appeal and differentiate their spaces. This behavior reflects humans' natural affinity for nature and the pleasurable feelings derived from interacting with natural elements. One relevant theory is Kaplan and Kaplan's Attention Restoration Theory, which posits that environments featuring elements that attract attention can mitigate mental fatigue. For instance, elements such as natural scenery visible from windows, fireplaces, and dynamic displays like aquariums and running water can reduce stress and enhance mental and physical health (Kaplan & Kaplan, 1989; Hartig *et al.*, 2003). Utilizing natural elements has been shown to reduce stress, aggression, and blood pressure while enhancing positive emotions (Hartig *et al.*, 2003; Hamid & Babamiri, 2011). These factors directly contribute to both mental and physical health, underscoring the importance of integrating environmental attractiveness and enjoyment into residential complex design.

Diverse Spaces and Activities and their Impact on Physical and Mental Health: The presence of diverse recreational, communal, and service spaces, along with varied activities within residential complexes, significantly influences residents' physical and mental health. In complexes lacking such diversity, residents often take initiatives to introduce variety and dynamism. For example, some organize art classes for different age groups, while others engage in team sports and group activities, promoting interaction and diversity within the community. Wandersman and Florin argue that community involvement through participation signifies individuals' life goals and reflects their health status. Similarly, Gamson suggests that engaging in social activities contributes to personal identity development and self-understanding (Wandersman & Florin, 2000, cited by Yazdan Panah & Nikvorz, 2014). Research has also demonstrated that limited social participation correlates with negative health outcomes (Herzog *et al.*, 2002). Therefore, the presence of diverse spaces and activities in complexes, due to their positive psychological effects and attraction for residents, directly impacts mental health, while the availability of sports facilities and encouragement of physical activity significantly benefits physical health. Together, these factors play a positive role in enhancing residents' physical and mental well-being.

Safety and Security of the Environment and its Effect on Physical and Mental Health: In the design of residential complexes, ensuring the presence of supervised, secure spaces, implementing social security measures, using appropriate barriers like walls and fences, and providing suitable flooring to facilitate mobility can create psychological and physical safety for residents. In complexes where a sense of security is lacking, residents may enclose their terraces or windows completely, reflecting their need for increased psychological security. Such instances highlight the critical importance of prioritizing security in residential complex design to empower residents with control over their local activities (Talebi & Kalantari, 1996). The absence of psychological security can indirectly affect residents' physical health. Research conducted in Chicago neighborhoods has shown that high levels of violence and inadequate physical security confine individuals to their homes, limiting physical activity (Krieger & Higgins, 2002). Thus, attention to safety and security in designing residential

complex spaces directly impacts residents' mental and physical health by fostering peace of mind and ensuring physical safety within the environment.

Environmental Comfort and its Effect on Physical and Mental Health: Environmental comfort encompasses factors such as air quality, temperature and humidity levels, adequate ventilation, noise control, optimal lighting during day and night, and prevention of intrusive light. These elements significantly influence residents' physical and mental well-being in residential complexes. Evans identifies built environment features affecting mental health, including congestion, noise pollution, air quality, and light levels (Evans, 2003, cited by Tabatabaian & Tamnai, 2012). Residents often take measures to improve their living conditions, such as mitigating bothersome light levels in their units. Studies have demonstrated that excessive light can induce mental stimulation and stress (Evans & McCoy, 1998). Conversely, optimal natural lighting has beneficial cognitive and psychological effects, including reducing depression and arousal (Veitch *et al.*, 1991; Kripke *et al.*, 1983; Boubekri *et al.*, 2014). Therefore, optimal use of lighting in spaces is essential for maintaining residents' mental and physical health in residential complexes. Moreover, considering climatic conditions, the use of heating, cooling, and air conditioning systems in buildings is crucial for enhancing environmental comfort and ensuring residents' well-being. Psychologists assert that elevated temperatures and humidity levels in architectural spaces can provoke irritability, stress, negative reactions, and aggressive behaviors among occupants (Bell, 1981, 2005; Bell & Green, 1982). Hence, attention to environmental factors such as suitable temperatures, humidity levels, adequate lighting, and appropriate spatial density directly and indirectly impacts health. Thus, incorporating these factors into the design of residential complex spaces can positively contribute to residents' health.

Privacy and its Impact on Mental and Social Health: In designing different spaces within residential complexes, consideration of desired privacy, respect for privacy, spatial hierarchy, clear territorial demarcation, tranquility, and noise reduction can positively affect residents' health. Observing residents' behaviors in complex environments underscores the significance of solitude and privacy as essential factors influencing their lives. Residents sometimes take steps to minimize visibility into their living spaces from various vantage points, enhancing their privacy within their residential units. Additionally, during communal hours, some residents prefer secluded corners of the complex open spaces, away from public view, for relaxation and leisure activities, highlighting their desire for privacy. The theory of Attention Restoration posits that individuals require minimal distractions and some degree of solitude to effectively engage in activities, attain mental refreshment, and achieve mental reconstruction (Evans & McCoy, 1998). Establishing clear territorial boundaries and respecting privacy can enhance personal security, reduce social conflicts, and mitigate neighborhood issues (Marcus & Sarkissian, 1988). When individuals or groups can cultivate desired solitude within their spaces, they gain control over their social interactions (Evans & McCoy, 1998). Therefore, considering the element of privacy in the design of residential complex spaces significantly influences individuals' psyche, efficiency, and interactions among residents, thereby playing a pivotal role in enhancing social and mental health.

Social Interactions and their Impact on Social Health: In residential complexes, the existence of sociable spaces facilitating interaction among different age groups can effectively contribute to social health while positively impacting residents' mental health. In surveyed residential complexes, residents frequently gather in communal spaces during specific times of the day, forming small social clusters. These clusters often congregate around playgrounds or children's educational areas. Some individuals engaged in solitary activities within the communal areas, such as reading near children's play zones or other shared spaces, indicating residents' inclination toward social engagement. Studies indicate that moderate crowding may be favorable, as individuals sometimes seek company and derive enjoyment from social interactions (Walden & Forsyth, 1981). Social health encompasses evaluating positive and negative meaningful behaviors in relation to others, as well as assessing the quality of relationships with family, peers, and social groups. It encompasses

individuals' internal responses to stimuli, feelings, thoughts, and behaviors indicative of their satisfaction or dissatisfaction with life and their social environment (Larson, 1993). Therefore, fostering meaningful social interactions within residential complex environments can significantly enhance residents' social health by positively impacting their well-being.

6- Conclusion

The concept of healing through the environment is a pivotal topic that has long been deliberated in spaces like hospitals and gardens. This concept also holds practical implications in housing. Today, with the recognition of sick building syndrome and the emergence of health issues associated with home environments, the importance of prioritizing health in residential spaces has become increasingly apparent. The aim of the current research is to investigate the factors influencing the design of residential complexes with a focus on enhancing residents' general health. In this regard, efforts were made to identify and examine these factors affecting residents' health in residential complexes. According to the research findings, these components include diverse spaces and activities, environmental pleasantness and attractiveness, safety and security, environmental comfort, privacy, and social interactions. Incorporating these components into the design of residential complexes can positively impact residents' overall health. Therefore, it is recommended that designers consider the following aspects when designing residential complexes: creating versatile spaces conducive to diverse activities and social interactions across all age groups; ensuring safety and security with appropriate flooring, lighting, and effective use of barriers and protection; integrating natural elements and creating appealing landscapes; addressing air quality, temperature, and humidity control in the environment; optimizing natural and artificial lighting to desired levels; and respecting visual and acoustic privacy while providing opportunities for solitude in spaces. By incorporating these considerations into the design of residential complexes, the attractiveness of spaces for users increases, and the designed environment can effectively contribute to improving residents' general health. Finally, recognizing the importance of prioritizing health in residential space design, it is hoped that architects and designers will take steps towards enhancing residents' overall health through future designs of residential complexes. The maintenance of public health ultimately contributes to societal well-being, yielding positive outcomes across various dimensions of society.

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